

UNLEASHING THE POWER OF AI FOR HEMATOLOGICAL DISEASES

An open hub for clinicians and researchers to work together defining, developing and validating AI models to improve the way we currently diagnose and treat hematological diseases

DIAGNOSIS

AI algorithms for early identification of high-risk individuals

PROGNOSIS

Predictions for insight on disease development

TREATMENT

Clinical decision support models for risk stratification

OUR VISION

Our privacy-by-design approach relies on a Federated Learning framework to ensure that no patient data ever leaves clinical sites and offers security in all data exchanges, model training and storage

A new paradigm built on robust, ethical agreements to bring community members together through explainable AI, enabling collaborative, cross-border data sharing that is standard-compliant

THE ONBOARDING PROCESS

INTERESTED IN JOINING? HERE'S HOW

- STEP 1 - Online application form**
Institution name & PI
No. datasets & data formats
Consents already in place
- STEP 2 - Signing the agreement**
Legal considerations & signatures
- STEP 3 - Evaluation**
Data assessment (relevance, scope & quality)
Consensus
Additional clarifications
- STEP 4 - Preparing your data**
Data dictionary
Specific data provisions
- ONBOARDING COMPLETE!**

Check out our **Associate Members Onboarding Handbook** for more details

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

Transforming the response to Hematological Diseases by sizing the power of Artificial Intelligence

Follow us!

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In collaboration with

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ADVANCING RESEARCH IN RARE DISEASES

At GenoMed4All, we are devoted to expanding the landscape of personalized medicine in rare diseases to enhance diagnostic capacity, assess treatment options and predict outcomes in rare diseases.

BECOMING AN ASSOCIATED MEMBER

OUR MANIFESTO

Fighting against data scarcity & fragmentation

Advocating for data quality & reliability

Pushing the boundaries on multimodal data pooling

Leading the way in distributed scaling up

Building & nurturing an active community

WHAT DO WE OFFER?

- Privileged access to GenoMed4All's platform & AI sandbox (models & algorithms)
- Dedicated space on our website to showcase Associate Members
- Full academic credit & co-authorship on publications where your data plays a role
- Contribute to our EOSC connection with metadata & aggregated data

THE PLATFORM

OPERATIONAL MODES

For clinicians

A local decision support system to input new prospective and retrospective patient data, extracting insights from an ever-learning model

For researchers

An AI workplace to explore datasets, develop, test and train new models on real-world data using our Federated Learning environment

METADATA & DATASET BROWSER

PREDICTIVE DISEASE MODELS

MODEL TESTING & VALIDATION

KEY FEATURES

- Explore the catalogue of datasets available for training federated learning models
- Extend the federation by including new nodes
- Validate models by running several checks when they are uploaded
- Run federated learning tasks by combining models with data chunks with common schemas. Tasks get queued up and automatically run when they are scheduled
- Gather the resulting parameters
- Secure the federation through access control mechanisms via IAM
- Explore the lists of available models in the model registry

OUR USE CASES

MYELODYSPLASTIC SYNDROMES

Prevention based on genomic screening
Omics-based classification and prognosis
Omics-based clinical decision making
Drug repurposing

SICKLE CELL DISEASE RADeep

Omics-based classification and prognosis
AI model to predict risk scores for cerebral silent infarct, acute chest syndrome and recurrent vaso-occlusive events
AI-based radiomics for imaging diagnosis of cerebral silent infarct

MULTIPLE MYELOMA

Understand disease complexity
Identify evolution dynamics
Study risk progression
Integrate radiomics and radiogenomics

DATA CATEGORIES

Demographic data

e.g., age, sex, race, ethnicity, height, weight, other

Clinical parameters

e.g., previous diagnoses, treatment plans & medications, conditions/clinical manifestations, medical history, clinical trials data

Imaging data

e.g., MRI sequences, collection frequency

Laboratory data

GWAS data

Genomic data

e.g., Next Generation Sequencing, Microarray, Genome Wide Association, Copy Number Variations, DNA sequencing, RNA sequencing

Biobank samples

Point of sickling data

Other